

IMAGE SONIFICATION BASED ON OBJECT AND FEATURE EXTRACTION

Keunhyoung Luke Kim

Woon Seung Yeo

Audio and Interactive Media Lab,
Graduate School of Culture Technology,
KAIST, Korea

doiluvu@gmail.com

woony@kaist.edu

ABSTRACT

We introduce a new paradigm for image sonification based on extraction of abstract features. Unlike most image sonification examples that convert low-level raw data into sound, this method utilizes scale invariant feature transform (SIFT) for image abstraction to obtain higher-level information, thereby producing more robust results with a variety of images and visual transformations. To separate visual components from an image and enhance hierarchical information to SIFT features, the sonification also utilizes an image structure analysis algorithm. Being invariant to object-level changes such as rotating, moving, or scaling, sonified sound describe the characteristics of different polygons well. We first describe our sonification model with SIFT features, and discuss its performance.

1. INTRODUCTION

Sonification of visual information is a popular subject with many application areas. In addition to creating audiovisual art, image sonification techniques can provide a special “augmented reality” environment for the visually impaired by presenting live camera view as sound [1]. Moreover, certain visual features of images that are hardly noticeable by eyes can be easily heard and detected. This shows that auditory display an effective tool for diagnostics and/or data exploration of visual information

Sonification of “high-level” features abstracted from an image usually reduces sensitivity to minor visual changes and, compared to the raw data (e.g., bitmap pixels), can provide more meaningful information. When the level of abstraction becomes too high, however, it may become too purpose-specific and not generally applicable.

This paper deals with sonification of abstract image features – local key points that are used to recognize objects in computer vision techniques, and aims to suggest a new method for sonification of abstracted images which a) produces results that are reasonably invariant to visual transformations of abstract objects, and b) performs reasonably well with different kinds of images (e.g., typical

photos, still-life, abstract paintings, etc.). The method separates visual objects in an image and sonifies local features of each object using additive synthesis. Since local features lack of structural information, we used Suzuki’s structure analysis algorithm [2] to group them into objects. Each object is regarded as a tone that consists of one or more harmonics that are determined by the features of the object. Then the tones are placed separately in time and properly localized.

To obtain desired features and design characteristic timbre for each object, we use scale invariant feature transform (SIFT) – a well-known visual object recognition algorithm that produces abstracted image features to compare or find out objects in images [3]. SIFT uses differences between multiple Gaussian-blurred images to find the “key features”, and the direction, magnitude and position of each key feature are used as parameters. Image features generated by SIFT are invariant to image translation, scaling, rotation, and are partially invariant to illumination changes as well as affine or 3-D projection: this is analogous to the properties of neural responses in inferior temporal cortex in primate vision [3], an allows us to extract more invariant and meaningful information from images.

2. RELATED RESEARCH

2.1 Image Sonification

Image Sonification is a relatively recent branch of data sonification. The idea of data transformation from image to sound is interesting and challenging for their dimensional and perceptual differences.

Examples of direct, low-level image to sound mapping include raster scanning [4], which is one of the most deeply studied techniques of image sonification with notable follow-up research. The mechanism is bidirectional and reversible: each image pixel corresponds to an audio sample in a row-by-row manner. This technique is useful for analysis of pitch- or frequency-related features of audio, but its linear scanning paradigm limits the feature of displaying information on visual “objects” in images.

Some researchers tried to extract more “abstract” information from images to overcome this limitation of sonifying raw data. Payling et al used basic image processing techniques to extracted local color information to generate music clips [5]. However, the information extracted was too simple and results were not generally applicable. A more advanced approach can be found in

[6]: here the authors extracted and sonified the edge information to help visually impaired “hear” the overall structure of images. It worked partially for simple and nicely processed images, but had problems with rather complex ones. Edwards et al worked on a purpose-specific image sonification of problematic biological cells from medical imaging data for diagnostic purpose [7].

2.2 Object Sonification

Similar to our work featured in this paper, some techniques have been suggested to enhance data exploration experience by providing auditory displays of virtual objects for sonification of symbolic information. For example, Shelley et al provided multimodal feedback for interaction with a virtual object [8]: they proposed four categories of sound abstraction and sonification methods from physical models to earcons. Despite the lack of detailed research on sonification method, this work presents a useful insight into levels of abstraction for object sonification.

3. SONIFICATION MODEL

Our sonification process takes two steps: 1) data extraction from images and 2) sonification of extracted data.

3.1 Data Extraction

While the major ingredient of this sonification is SIFT feature data, it represents only local characteristics of an image and lacks structural information. Sonified results from these features altogether may sound very chaotic and unrecognizable. Here we use image structure analysis techniques to obtain more “object level” point-of-view and conserve generality of application.

Once SIFT features are extracted, they are grouped into objects according to their positions and the result of structure analysis.

3.1.1 SIFT

With SIFT algorithm, image features are extracted in the following steps.

First, a “pyramid” of the original image, which consists of differences between multiple level Gaussian blurred images, is constructed. Each level of pyramid is a difference image of two adjacent levels.

Second, local maxima and minima from the pyramid are detected. The pyramid is three-dimensional; two dimensions are analogous to the dimensions of the original image, and one comes from the level of the pyramid. These points are stored as candidates of local image features.

Third, “weaker” points, including those with too low contrast or those whose gradients are along the edges of the image, are removed. Then the remaining points are finally marked as local features.

Lastly, the directions and the magnitudes of image gradients at each feature point are calculated. These properties are used as image comparison cue in object detection application, and as harmonics of tones representing each object in this sonification.

Figure 1. Original images (left) and their SIFT features shown as arrows (right).

SIFT feature describe characteristics of objects using color gradient and it successfully find the same object from different images even they are scaled or transformed. Example of SIFT extraction is shown in figure 1. The features found from the original images on left are shown on right. For polygon objects, SIFT features usually have directions according to each side of polygons. Upper two images show a triangle and SIFT features of a triangle. Each arrow represents a brightness change from dark to bright color. The size of arrow means amount of change. In the triangle, there are three sudden color changes, or gradients, since there are three sides in a triangle. In the lower images, there is a rectangle with 5 large arrows. The arrow heading to 2 o’clock is an exceptional one, which comes from position of the rectangle. These exceptional features can be rejected by limiting the SIFT feature extracting algorithm. Still, the four orthogonal large arrows strongly represent presence of a rectangle.

3.1.2 Representation of Objects

Objects represented by SIFT feature are high identifiable, but SIFT feature itself does not store edge or structural information and it cannot be determined whether a feature is in an object or not, where a need for image processing to extract structural information arises. Edge information is retrieved by the difference of Gaussian method [9]. With edge information, the structure of the image is analyzed by Suzuki’s algorithm [2]. If an edge makes a closed loop, it is regarded as an object and features inside the loop become characteristic of the object. Result of structure analysis is a tree-like data of detected closed loops. Figure 2 shows the outlines of each object and which SIFT features belongs to which objects.

Figure 2. Borders of object area marked in red (left), and the SIFT features with object borders (right).

Finally we obtain a list of the objects that contains SIFT features. Additionally, magnitudes of each feature are normalized so that they do not exceed 1. Direction values are also scaled to fit into the range from 0 to 4. In the sonification step, each object is interpreted as a musical note played by an instrument. Features of an object determine the frequency and harmonics of its tone.

3.2 Sonification

3.2.1 Sonification of Each Object

We use additive synthesis method for sonification, where each feature corresponds to a sinusoid. Frequency of a sinusoid is determined by the gradient direction of its according feature, as

$$f = f_{base} \cdot 2^{direction}, \quad (1)$$

where f_{base} is the fundamental frequency and $direction$ is the normalized direction value of each feature. Since the direction value ranges from 0 to 4, a 90 degree difference between two features results in separation by one octave in frequency. Likely, an ideal rectangle will have a fundamental frequency, the second, the third, and the fourth octave sinusoids.

The amplitude of each sinusoid determined by the gradient magnitudes and decreases gradually. Sinusoids of an objects rings simultaneously, which makes them heard as a tone with various harmonics. For a single triangle (see figure 1 and 2), there are 3 major features with different directions. Figure 3 shows the sonified result of a triangle: here we can notice three major frequency peaks in the spectrum.

Figure 3. Sonification result of a single triangle (See figure 1 for the original image): the waveform (top) and the spectrum (bottom). Screenshots were taken using Audacity.

3.2.2 Composition of Objects

Objects in the 2-dimensional space of visual domain should be arranged over time in the auditory domain. Here, the vertical position of an object in an image determines when its corresponding sound will be played. More specifically, playback of an object sound is delayed according to how far it is placed from the top edge of the image. Horizontal position of an object is used for stereo panning. The position information of objects can be also used for more sophisticated sound localization.

Figure 4 shows the sonified result of an image with two different objects, which is shown in figure 1 (bottom left). In this example, it is clearly shown that the tone of the triangle comes before that of the rectangle with panning characteristics determined by their horizontal positions.

Figure 4. Sonification result of a triangle and a rectangle (see figure 1, bottom left for the original image). The waveforms (top) and their spectrograms (bottom) are shown. The tone for the triangle rings first from right, then the tone for the rectangle rings from left. Screenshots were taken using Audacity.

4. RESULT

We used five different sets of images to test the performance of the sonification model. Sonified results as well as the original images can be found at the author’s website.¹

4.1 Basic Shapes

Images with simple shapes (i.e., triangles and rectangles) were tested for comparison of basic transformations. Test image sets were created by transposing, rotating, and scaling the original images.

The results show that, in spite of these geometric transformations applied to generate the test image sets, we can obtain very similar sounds from the same shape, and distinguishable ones between different shapes. Transposition featured results with the least different (except timing and panning). While rotation may affect spectral distribution of the sound, the results are still recognizable. Scaling, obviously, can change the loudness of the sonified result.

4.2 Combination of Basic Shapes

This time we put two or more shapes in each image. Combinations include 1) two squares, 2) two triangles, 3) one square and one triangle, 4) two square and one triangle, 5) one square and two triangle, and 6) two squares and two triangles. From the sonified results, we can easily tell if the image contains two or more shapes. In addition,

¹ http://aimlab.kaist.ac.kr/~dilul/research/SIFTSo_nification

tion, the listener should be able to notice the type of the shapes and their positions with basic information on the mapping mechanism.

4.3 More Complex Basic Shapes

We further tested more complex forms of triangles and rectangles. Some of them were “decorated”, some were abstract paintings, while others were real photos of simple objects. Simpler examples result in sounds that are highly similar to the first set of examples. More complex shapes such as abstract paintings produce quite different tones, but certain level of similarity can still be found.

4.4 Patterns

General application to objectless images (such as patterns) is one of the important long-term objectives of this research. While polygon-based patterns generate stable and shape-representing sounds, line-based and irregular patterns are less recognizable. However, similarity between similar patterns can also be noticed from the results. At this point, our conclusion is that this method can generate a tune of pattern images with unique characteristics: this will be investigated further.

4.5 Complex Images

Some highly-complex images, such as photos of complex objects and paintings, were also sonified for comparison. While it can hardly be said that the results are generally evocative for complex images, some of them featured sound that are reminiscent of certain local characteristics of the images. If the complex images can be more simplified using filters or image processing techniques such as “posterize” or “cartoon filter”, they should produce more recognizable sounds.

5. CONCLUSIONS

This research aims to propose a sonification method that enables the listener to recognize objects in image regardless of their positions and visual transformations. To this end, we proposed the use of SIFT features as a new way to sonify feature-level information of images. The suggested model partially achieved the goal for sonification of simple objects, and showed certain characteristics of mid-level abstracted images.

In summary, sonification of image feature information showed advantages in keeping object-level characteristic as it is more robust to object-level changes such as scaling, moving, or transposing an object. It can also deal with certain level of image textures. Not only these characteristics are useful for previously attempted image sonification works, but also they show a strong potential for new application areas. The technique catches essential visual characteristics and makes identifiable sound, which can be used for audio support for the visually impaired, or generation of earcons from simplified images.

For further research, more object recognition techniques (including as edge detections) will be introduced to the model to provide even more abstraction to the data. Other sonification models and synthesis methods will also be

incorporated and tested to find out methods with more natural and evocative results.

6. REFERENCES

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